

Manual for the Methodology “Narrative Ethical Scenario Building”

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To be cited as: Kaiser, M., Rauhala, M., Pfister, J., Ziouvelou, X., Manos, I., Garani-Papadatos, T, Mollaki, V. (2026). “Manual for the Methodology: A Narrative Ethical Scenario Process”; CHANGER Project, working documents.

This is the abbreviated version of the concept note on Narrative Ethical Scenario Building. For all explanatory context we refer to this concept note. In this practical manual we shall focus on the What-to-do, Why-to-do-it, How-to-do-it, and Who's-going to-do-it, with only the bare essentials, capturing the idealized abstract standard cases. We are going to present a methodology – or a tool if you prefer – to assess the ethical challenges in a research project. We call it the “Narrative Ethical Scenario Methodology” or “NESSEN” for short.

1. Executive Summary

The text provides a practical manual for the construction and inclusion of a narrative ethical scenario process (NESSEN). This tool / method can be used for inclusion of ethical aspects and value dilemmas in descriptions of possible futures of an area. It is chosen when the segment of reality that is under study is highly complex and the research outcomes are uncertain at the start of the research. Instead of neglecting ethical issues, this tool is an encouragement for researchers and stakeholders / users to engage in scenario construction which is then amendable to ethical / value assignments. Scenario processes are already widely used, but in this case, it is argued that the process has the potential to presently engage with the possible futures that one wants to aim at or those which one wants to avoid. This can then guide inter- and transdisciplinary research characterized by high complexity and uncertainty. Given this framework, the results are more in line with transformative research and policy implementation.

2. Introduction

*‘Scenarios are stories about the future,
but their purpose is to make better decisions in the present.’
Ged Davis*

Let us assume you plan a larger, typically inter- or transdisciplinary research projects with stakeholders that will last a significant period of time, often between 5 and 10 years. Time will be spent on planning the project, on writing an application for funding, on getting all the stakeholders involved in the process on board, on doing the actual research, and finally evaluating the outcomes and concrete policy implications of the project. The task of planning all this is admittedly demanding; assessing the possible ethical challenges that you will face during this project is even more challenging. Perhaps you can foresee that the funder might send you a check-list for possible ethical issues involved in the project or that there might be a demand to have this project’s ethical issues assessed by an ethics committee (REC). In some countries a self-assessment of these issues might be sufficient. But seriously reflecting about this question you might find two things which you consider important: First, the ethical issues might evolve during the course of the project, at various stages, and they cannot really be foreseen as different partners / users might react differently: there is inherent **uncertainty** about the ethical issues the project will be confronted with; Second, the project is addressing a problem area where several different systems interact and the causal interactions might very well be non-linear and unpredictable: in other words there is an inherent **complexity** in the subject of the planned research.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, under grant agreement No 101131683.

If the existing measures to address ethical issues in a research project with high uncertainty and complexity are recognized as insufficient and non-adequate, what then can you do?

The following text provides a practical manual that has a focus on: What-to-Do, Why-to-Do-It, and Who's-Going-to-Do-It? The text provides a manual for one of the tools or methodologies which are developed in the CHANGER project. The manual is aiming at a practical solution how to deal with the challenge described above. We call it the **“Narrative Ethical Scenario Process”** or abbreviated as **“NESCEN”** for short. The theoretical background and methodological support framework are described in more detail in the related Concept Note on NESCEN. Here we introduce only the bare essentials of the method.

3. Whom do we address? Who is our target audience?

This methodology addresses primarily the research practitioners and the ethical committees, in particular those who take a leading role in the design and performance of an inter- or transdisciplinary research projects. Indirectly it will also affect the research funders and publication channels as they take a strong interest in how ethical issues are addressed in the research they are associated with. Finally, it is also of interest to all those individuals and units that will be involved in such a research activity even though not all of them will be leading the process but instead participate in the activities of the NESCEN.

The researchers who carry out a complex research project (what kind of research is described below) will have to implement NESCEN during the course of their project. Typically, they will have to implement NESCEN with some or all of the laypeople, the users or concerned parties of the planned research project. The researchers will typically also operate in a team, preferably in an interdisciplinary team. In a few cases of restricted complexity, NESCEN could be done in a scaled-down version by the researcher or a small group of them.

Disciplinary background of the researchers should not be relevant, as the method can be learned by anyone. However, **interdisciplinary competencies in the research team** are recommended.

But knowledge about the NESCEN method and a principal insight into how the NESCEN might be operative in a given research project will also be important for all the **assessors and reviewers** (of ethics) of a given research project. They will have to check whether the full potential of NESCEN is realized in the given project they assess.

4. Purpose and Scope

The purpose of the following text about the NESCEN is to suggest a practical way out of the ethical conundrum when the research task ahead is strongly characterized by (i) inherent uncertainty about the ensuing procedures and outcomes, and (ii) about the

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inherent complexities of the system under study. It is recognized that good ethics in research enhances the quality of the research outcomes, and it strengthens the robustness and transformative power of the research outcomes. The research task is therefore guided by producing results that are fit-for-purpose, and that includes consideration of ethics and societal values.

The scope of the research under consideration can be regional, national, European or even global. Scope will have an effect on the level of detail and scale, and the boundaries of the systems that are considered. However, in principle similar processes of NESCCEN can be initiated at all these levels. As a matter of fact, several processes resembling NESCCEN have already been performed at some selected levels but mostly without specifically addressing ethical issues or value dilemmas.

5. When to use SM? What are the typical topics?

The method is suitable for a select group of experts and laypeople that wants to develop ethically adequate strategies for dealing with various possible future developments. The method might be a part of **ethics by design** in projects where the future impact of the results is hard to assess with a high level of confidence, where outcomes for good and bad could be imagined, and where there might be disagreement about what is a good and intended result and what is a bad unintended result. The method has a time perspective into the future of usually 5-15 years, sometimes less, sometimes more.

NESCCEN is recommended for use for all research projects with high complexity, uncertain outcomes of potential high social impact, and for all transdisciplinary research which includes a variety of knowledge systems and a diversity of value landscapes. This we can find both in technological innovation projects, in social science policy development projects, and in environmental planning projects. Common is normally the involvement of non-scientific actors as e.g. user-groups, professional organisations, industry, policy makers or indigenous groups.

Note that for instance the so-called action-research or participative research with potential policy implications will always fall under this scheme. The crucial aspect here is the link between knowledge generation and the potential for impact on future social realities.

Checklist for when to use NESCCEN:

- Is the planned research characterized by high complexity? And:
- The project outcomes are very uncertain but have potentially significant policy implications (on a local, regional, national or global scale); And:
- The planned project will potentially cross several knowledge systems and / or reveal a diversity in the value-landscapes among the concerned parties.

In order for NESCCEN to be effective for deliberations about preferred futures, NESCCEN needs to be carefully planned. NESCCEN needs to be a crucial and explicit element in the project design / description that is to be supported by funders and participants. This is the first appearance of NESCCEN in the project. The second appearance is then during the execution phase of the research. Here it is preferably placed in the early phase of the project, but after the partners have an initial grasp on their tasks ahead. The final appearance is after all the research is done and the results are in. Then a second running of

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the NESCCEN is needed to see if anything from the first running needs to be adjusted before one turns to follow up with decision makers.

Thus, we suggest that planning and conducting a NESCCEN happens at least at three different phases of the research:

Figure 1. When ethical scenario process is inserted.

6. Methodology and Structure of the Presentation.

The methodology used here is mainly philosophical and interdisciplinary as it tries to combine insights from ethics, law, and social sciences, and translate them to possible uses in inter- and transdisciplinary science, and Big Data research. The text starts out with general constraints that the tool needs to implement before it moves on to a sketch of practical applications. The text provides the principal pillars of such applications while it leaves some of the more practical aspects open for the context of the users. The methodology in NESCCEN is based on a review of theoretical frameworks that are already well-entrenched in social science, but the practical application is condensed to a more intuitive framework which are easily comprehended even without knowledge of all the previous work on scenarios.

7. The Manual

Note that this manual will be supplemented by a (published) concept note.

A **narrative ethical scenario process (NESCCEN)** (or we may hereafter simply talk about a scenario) is a method which aims at fostering deliberation on plausible futures and their ethical pros and cons. Such a scenario works from the insight that the future is not simply a prolongation of present trends but might be determined by surprising events and causes. In other words, it includes the basic uncertainty of future developments with some uncertainties resulting from the inherent complexity of the research subject. The method of narrative ethical scenario building needs input from various experts and stakeholders and is to be carefully prepared. A NESCCEN provides people with an easy-to-

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understand narrative of possible future developments so that their choices of strategy to attain one of these becomes more goal-oriented.

Note that sometimes, in some social science work, scenarios are constructed in a very loose and common-sense manner, without making use of a more systematic approach. Here we want to stress that there can actually be a sound methodology behind the construction of scenarios, and one should make use of that as far as possible and as much as practical constraints allow. We are, however, aware that constraints may follow from the project design that can impact the rigour of the method. Our appeal is to make it as rigorous an approach as possible, but also as much understandable and simple for the stakeholders as in practice achievable.

Graph inspired by Ulrich Gölücke

Figure 2: Scenarios between certainty and ignorance.

The above graph depicts the imaginary space where scenarios work best. Take as example weather predictions. Typically, we have data enough and some sound knowledge to use models to predict the weather in an area for some time ahead, up to typically 2-3 weeks. But the farther we go into the future the higher are the uncertainties. With some knowledge, some data, and significant uncertainties we enter the realm of scenarios. If we go farther into the future with the possibility of some more radical changes in our parameters (e.g. due to climate change etc) the uncertainties become dominant. We then enter the realm of utopia, where we can be driven by hope or sometimes fatalism (dystopia), but not enough to let us be guided by these perspectives in our daily affairs. Scenarios on the other hand are the tools we can use to prepare us for a variable possible future which is not so far ahead of us and of which we know at least something.

7.1 What are the expected outcomes of applying NESSEN?

The outcome of such an exercise would be a picture or rather a narrative of possible divergent futures, cast in a rough narrative which is often graphically represented, and with different impacts on goods and bads. Thus, it might form a basis for designing a common strategy how to avoid outcomes that one does not deem as overall beneficial. For possible

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sub-optimal outcomes, one has the chance to prepare ethical guidelines / regulations or other embedding frameworks which can limit the most unwanted outcomes. It helps to streamline the project and innovative knowledge activities towards visions which gain wide support among all or most parties. It does not require a truly consensual outcome, but merely a robust outcome that has a potential of wider support.

In this sense, one should note that the narrative ethical scenarios are not ethical algorithms. Judgement is required. But the main function of the method is as a guide to adequate knowledge production in a team, and to avoid framings which in reality are too narrow (often the result of disciplinary siloes), or to merely follow deterministic technocratic “imperatives”. Narrative ethical scenarios broaden the option space for the choice of desired futures as the outcome of the research.

7.2 What the NESSEN cannot do.

The method does not end in a normative recommendation. It calls for individual and social **judgement** to evaluate the scenarios and navigate a way to deal adequately with the corresponding decisions. Ethical considerations might apply to both the process of the research and the outcome. Dealing with fair procedures and other relevant ethical considerations in the collaborative research (respect, transparency, equity, etc.) is **not** covered by the scenarios. This needs to be clarified when building up the team.

7.3 How do we do the NESSEN in practice? Planning and execution.

The NESSEN is executed in a few but crucial steps. These steps are in succession to each other. Basically, the NESSEN follows the usual recommendations for how to construct useful scenarios, supplemented by an ethical value assignment based on recognizing the diversity in the value landscapes of the affected parties and social groups. The research participants need to be aware of these steps in the planning while the ethical assessors (for instance a Research Ethics Committee - REC) during the funding phase of the project only need to check whether the responsible party has the capacity, knowledge and willingness to conduct these steps. Here are the steps in internal logical succession:

- i. The first precondition is that all research parties, including non-academic partners (indigenous groups etc.) have agreed (normally in deliberations of some length) on a common **problem** formulation.
- ii. Provide a **tentative value-landscape** resp. a mapping of the social values that are relevant to subject area, i.e. the problem and possible solutions.
- iii. All research parties try to **describe the system** they will be studying by naming the **elements** of the interacting system, by naming the **relations** between all these elements, by **characterizing the relations** whether they are unidirectional, multi-directional, and whether they **increase** or **decrease** an effect link.¹
- iv. Identify **major influences/ drivers** on the whole system or major parts of it and describe them either as “**push-factors**” (i.e. those major influences that drive the

¹ Cf.: Donella H. Meadows (2008). *Thinking in Systems – A primer*. Chelsea Green Publishing Company.]

system towards some change) and “**pull-factors**” (i.e. those major influences which provide indications where the change ought to go).²

- v. Identify **major uncertainties** in the knowledge of some of the details in the system and the dynamics of the whole system. Uncertainties can be described with the help of a traffic-light representation: green (little uncertainty), orange (some substantial uncertainties), or red (consistently high uncertainties with all aspects). Note that uncertainties can be: a) stochastic behavior of the natural system, b) statistical uncertainty in the data, c) methodological uncertainty in the harvesting and reliability of the data, or d) epistemic uncertainty when we are uncertain whether we are measuring or looking at the right indicator in the first place. It can also designate sheer ignorance.³
- vi. **Combine the effect of the major drivers with the major uncertainties.** See what conceivable futures may arise from them, describing them qualitatively and in rough outline. If possible, provide a **narrative** and / or **image** that gives you the **relevant scenarios**. There will normally be between two (e.g. worst and best case) and several scenarios. If necessary, simplify them for pragmatic reasons.
- vii. Refer to some useful knowledge about the **ethical value-landscape** of the individuals in the system you are interested in. These value-landscapes should list and give weight to the most prominent values held by the individuals.
- viii. **Assign** how the **most prominent values are represented in each of the scenarios**. It is the difference in the weight to particular values which provides the ethical decision basis for the policy that decision makers will embrace. Think of for instance differences in equity versus safety versus freedom that come out in the scenarios.
- ix. **End of ethical assessment task.**

7.3.1 Briefly on systems.

A system consists always of a number of elements (e.g. actors) – the domain - and a number of relationships (e.g. x pays y; x promotes y; y decreases influence of z; etc.) between these elements – the interactions. Some of the relationships may be one-directional ($x \rightarrow y$), while others may be two-directional ($x \leftrightarrow y$). A system also includes the basic function this system is designed for. A system for chemical production may thus be different from a system for crime prevention or the food system, even when many of the involved actors may be identical. One wants to know the input, the output and the processes that characterize the system. These systems can be open (energy and matter

² An example of a model for transformative change using this approach is given as the “Turtle model” in: Kaiser, M., Cretella, A., Scherfer, C., Lam, M.E. (forthcoming 2026).

‘A “Turtle Model” _of Food System Transformations: Embracing Citizens’ Diverse Values and Knowledge in Change Processes’, Food Ethics; prepublished on ArXiv 2025.

³ with expert help or note e.g. the NUSAP system for uncertainty mapping:

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NUSAP> or: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC31449> or: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16304945/>

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can enter), closed (energy can enter), or isolated (neither energy nor matter can enter). A system has an environment which is defined through what lies beyond its boundaries. The whole point of constructing the system is to get a quick overview of the dynamical capacities of the system you are interested in. You should end up with an informative visual representation of the system. Note that you need to decide where the boundaries of the system are. In reality, these systems quickly become highly complicated with many factors to consider. Completeness of the system is seldom required for scenario analysis, and one needs to make a pragmatic decision how much detail is really needed. Graphic simplified examples: the social system of higher education (here taken from: Gonzales, M. 2020. Systems Thinking for Supporting Students with Special Needs and Disabilities. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-33-4558-4>).

The social structure and social functions in a social system

7.3.2 Drivers and barriers

Scenarios are built by having a close look at major drivers of development. In other words, what initiates processes of change and what determines their envisaged outcomes? This is why one builds a system representation (model) to start with. In many cases these systems may be quite complex interrelations, and the sheer number of factors can be confusing, and one might lose the big picture out of sight. Completeness of the model / system is not the point here. One needs to focus on the major drivers and barriers which bring about or hamper change of the system.

We have already noted in the description of systems that some elements can normally be described as leverage points. i.e. elements with a high influence on other elements. Other nodes may stop processes between elements of the system. These are barriers. Normally it will do to identify some major drivers and barriers.

7.3.3 On uncertainty assessment

There are basically four types of uncertainty to consider: (1) natural stochastic processes; (2) statistical uncertainty; (3) methodological uncertainty; (4) epistemic uncertainty / ignorance.

(1) refers to natural, societal or economic processes which most often behave stochastically, often dependent on the time period which is of interest. Complex systems are an example of this. A switch from one state to another can occur and makes precise prediction impossible. Tipping points are an example.

(2) In statistical analysis uncertainty describes how the estimate might differ from the true value. We know of false-positive or false-negative outcomes. The expected degree of confidence in the outcome is typically set 0.05 which is a 95% chance to hit the true value.

(3) Methodological uncertainty is normally the reliability and validity of the measured data we use. Some phenomena are hard to measure directly or reliably (due to the instruments we might have to use). Often, we depend on indicators, even sometimes on composite indicators. Very abstract phenomena or phenomena which are indirectly inferred have high methodological uncertainty.

(4) Epistemological or epistemic uncertainty refers to a more principled lack of knowledge, sometimes sheer ignorance. We may simply not have any data to assess certain phenomena, though they are believed to be causally effective in some settings. Modelling safety in human-technology interactions (e.g. in nuclear power plants) is assumed to be dependent on the belief-states of people operating it, though these states are not accessible.

Many of these uncertainties can be more systematically assessed with some rather sophisticated methods (see in the Concept note). However, in many practical settings, particularly in a scenario building process, this degree of sophistication is not called for. Informal inputs from experts on specifics that are the building blocks of the existing knowledge about the system interactions may suffice. With the four uncertainty types in

mind, one may end up with a rough traffic light system for certain states, causes and effects which gives useful ideas what is more or less certain.

We include here one method, the NUSAP method (Pedigree analysis) how to represent uncertainty in a visual and intuitive manner. Note, however, that this is only an illustration of uncertainty representation; other approaches might work as well.

Box 1. Pedigree analysis

Pedigree analysis is part of the NUSAP (numeral unit spread assessment pedigree) system for uncertainty assessment (Funtowicz and Ravetz 1990, van der Sluijs *et al* 2005a, 2005b). Pedigree conveys an evaluative account of the production process of information, and indicates different aspects of the underpinning of the numbers and scientific status of the knowledge used. Pedigree is expressed by means of a set of pedigree criteria to assess these different aspects. Assessment of pedigree involves qualitative expert judgment and can be done in an expert workshop or in expert elicitation interviews. To minimize arbitrariness and subjectivity in measuring strength, a pedigree matrix is used to code qualitative expert judgments for each criterion into a discrete numeral scale from a low (0) to high (4) level of knowledge, with linguistic descriptions (modes) of each level on the scale. For example, the criterion ‘empirical basis’ has a scale running from ‘crude speculation (0)’ to ‘large sample of direct measurements (4)’. Each special sort of information has its own aspects that are key to its pedigree, so different pedigree matrices using different pedigree criteria can be used to qualify different sorts of information. An example of the outcome of a pedigree analysis applied to Netherlands national emission inventories is given in figure 2.

Figure 2. Pedigree chart (Wardekker *et al* 2008) for the emission monitoring calculations of three air pollutants in the Netherlands: NH₃ (van Gijlswijk *et al* 2003), VOC (van der Sluijs 2005) and PM₁₀ (Klopogge and van der Sluijs 2006). In all cases, models were part of the emission monitoring system.

7.3.4 Constructing the scenarios.

We quoted in the introduction that scenarios are **stories** about the future (with a function, namely, to help us manage the present). Thus, once we have gained some insight in the system we want to do research on, understood some of its major drivers and barriers, as well as able to assign some rough uncertainty assessment to them, we need to turn to the task of constructing several of these stories about the future, say 5 or 10 or 20 years from now (the bigger the time period is, the bigger are the uncertainties and the scenarios may not be that helpful).

This phase of the NESSEN could often use one or several persons from the “outside” with a “creative” background. A writer or a painter or an illustrator or similar is often of great help to spark off the discussion of the scenario stories. But it is not necessary. As long as the process with all the partners and users is open, transparent and inspiring to mobilize users’ creative minds, it will do.

One may ask: “Let us assume that these drivers here with all their constraints will be dominating a development into the future, how would different people describe this future?” It is important that the emerging story reflects the socio-political, socio-technical, socio-economic, and socio-cultural dimension of such a development. It is never merely technical or political.

We give an example from Norway in the Appendix 01.

7.3.5 How is ethical theory represented in this method?

Ethical theory enters through assignment of ethical values to alternatives; furthermore, a consideration of major ethical principles, like Equity or Precaution; consideration of variety in dominant ethical landscapes.

Therefore, it is essential that one conducts an initial mapping of ethical values; we call this also a mapping of the value-landscapes (cf. Kaiser 2024). These values should be used then in an evaluation of the ethical qualities in each of the projected scenarios. This can be done by initial surveys or interviews. Standard lists of social (personal) values from social psychology might be used to obtain a primer of relevant values to look for. Ranking between them might be done but is more complicated in terms of research methodology. The ethical values and principles will generally be hidden or implicit in the scenario description. These are narratives (or imaginaries, illustrations) which come close to what in narrative ethics is called lived experiences. Between two different scenarios there will be at least one ethical value / principle which differentiates them.

However, often each scenario will comprise some positive values and some more negative values. The tradeoffs between them should in the end be a deliberative process crossing the value-landscapes in society. One may also combine the scenarios with a process of an Ethical Matrix (or Ethical Delphi) to lay bare which ethical principles may be promoted or harmed in such a future development. See also specifics of Narrative Ethics.

8 The methodology at a glance

Figure 3. Overview of the timing of Methodology "Ethics Scenario Building".

Figure 4. Flowchart of ethical scenario building.

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10. Conclusions

We have here presented a process of scenario building which includes a narrative ethical focus. It is suited for an appraisal of ethical issues in research projects characterized by high complexity and uncertainty of research outcomes. In practice it should be included as a work task in the initial description of the project which may or may not be represented to an ethics committee (REC). The REC simply has to ascertain that the project includes an adequate ethics component and that the proposers show competency to do it. Then the first NESSEN has to be conducted with all stakeholders at the start / first phase of the project, following a brief attempt to survey relevant values. The stakeholders will in this basis to the scenario which answers best to the values (and benefits) one wants to achieve through the project work. In the final phase of the project, once the knowledge has been produced, all stakeholders return to the scenarios and ask if the project in fact has achieved the outcome it was intended to achieve. The result of this process is reported in the final documents. The methodology is open for a simplified approach or a more sophisticated approach, as may be appropriate for the scope and scale of the project. The narrative ethics approach behind this methodology is intended to ensure the multi-perspectivity represented in the group and the social robustness of its outcomes. At the same time, it deals explicitly with the values underlying the research work.

11. Appendix 1: A case study from 1999:

We intend to briefly mention and present one example of scenario planning process, an example from fishery policies:

M. Kaiser & E.-M. Forsberg (2001), "Assessing Fisheries – Using an Ethical Matrix in a Participatory Process.", *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics*, 14: 191-200.

A more sophisticated example with a mixed method approach for mapping stakeholder values is provided in the Concept Note.

The following slides depict the different stages in the scenario process, except the valuation part in the plenary. In this concrete example it was done with the ethical matrix, but it can be done differently, given that some societal values are shared by the stakeholders and attributed to the scenarios.

Worries for the future of Norwegian fisheries -> 2020?

*"What can really create difficulties for Norwegian Fisheries?"
Konsensus from the expert / lay working group:*

- 1) Little robustness / flexibility structure of the fleet (because bad regulations / rights)
- 2) Recruitment – access to expertise / active shipowners
- 3) Resource: inadequate management by administration of large variability in resources – wrong quotas
- 4) Market collapse or reduced access to markets because of financial, resource aspects and irrational factors
- 5) International / national finance & economy politics / - vil there be more liberalisation or will there be protectionism as counter reaction? No level-field competition / framework conditions.
- 6) Weakened legitimacy as consequence of fishery practices (use vs protection)
- 7) Weakened coastal economy and coastal culture.

**Verdi-
vurdering
av norske
fiskerier**

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Main areas for worries:

Analysis of major drivers in the total system: _

Horizontal axis short-term versus long-term administration towards 2020

1. No food scarcity / protein scarcity
2. Intern. Environmental values weaker than now
3. Fragmented and little coordinated treaties; war all-against-all
4. Short-term management of resources

1999

1. Scarcity of food / protein
2. Intern. Environmental values stronger
3. Coordinated and holistic treaties on resource outtake; Law of the Seas
4. Long-term management framework for resources.

1. *Strong innovation driver*: - framework for new technology implementation
2. International *Market-orientation* – brands and labels, marketing

1999

Vertical axis:
Adaptability and innovation in the Norwegian fishery sector and structure.

1. *Stability driven*: slow implementation of new technology
2. National *subsidies*, social justice and distribution

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Remark: The value assignment was made with the Ethical Matrix method after the scenarios were clear.

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